

*Каньовська Л.В.,**Ляхович О.Д.**Буковинський державний медичний університет*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13354364>**СУЧАСНІ АЛГОРИТМИ ЛІКУВАННЯ ВНУТРІШНІХ ХВОРОБ НА ОСНОВІ ДОКАЗОВОЇ МЕДИЦИНИ***Kaniowska L.V.,**Liakhovich O.D.**Bukovinian State Medical University***MODERN ALGORITHMS FOR THE TREATMENT OF INTERNAL DISEASES BASED ON EVIDENCE-BASED MEDICINE****Анотація.**

Проведення елективного курсу «Сучасні алгоритми лікування при захворюваннях внутрішніх органів» є одним з елементів в програмі підготовки студентів старших курсів. Він має на меті ознайомити студентів з сучасними протоколами ведення пацієнтів, заснованих на позиціях доказової медицини. Впровадження доказової медицини є важливим завданням для медичної спільноти, що допоможе підвищити якість медичної допомоги і підвищити її рівень.

Abstract.

Conducting the elective course "Modern algorithms of treatment for diseases of internal organs" is one of the elements in the training program of senior students. It aims to acquaint students with modern patient management protocols based on evidence-based medicine. The implementation of evidence-based medicine is an important task for the medical community, which will help improve the quality of medical care and increase its level.

Ключові слова: сучасні алгоритми, навчання, лікування, інтерактивні методи, доказова медицина.

Key words: modern algorithms, training, treatment, interactive methods, evidence-based medicine.

Main part. The professional training of a highly qualified specialist during training is aimed not only at the accumulation of theoretical knowledge, but also at the formation of clinical thinking and the ability to make balanced decisions under conditions of stress in a short period of time, which will contribute to increasing competitiveness in the conditions of the modern labor market. Classical forms of organization of the educational process give students the opportunity to accumulate theoretical knowledge, which, unfortunately, in the future, as experience shows, they cannot use in real conditions when interacting with a patient.

The program of the elective course "Modern algorithms for the treatment of internal diseases based on evidence-based medicine" aims to train specialists who possess a sufficient amount of theoretical knowledge and practical skills to carry out the most rational drug therapy of the patient taking into account his characteristics, possess the methodology of choosing the most effective and safe drugs, as well as their combinations, taking into account the individual characteristics of the organism, the course and form of the disease, the presence of concomitant pathology based on the principles of evidence-based medicine [1-3].

When studying the elective course "Modern algorithms for the treatment of internal diseases based on evidence-based medicine", the following topics will be studied:

1. Evidence-based medicine: basic concepts, principles and tasks. "Gold standards" of treatment in internal medicine.

2. Modern treatment algorithms in pulmonology
3. Modern treatment algorithms in cardiology and rheumatology
4. Modern treatment schemes in gastroenterology and nephrology

The relevance of studying the course "Modern treatment algorithms in internal medicine" is due to several factors, among which the rapid development of medicine plays an important role. New methods of diagnosis and treatment of internal diseases appear every year. In order to be effective in their work, therapists must keep abreast of the latest research and developments. The complexity of diagnosis and treatment of internal diseases does not lose its relevance. Many internal diseases have similar symptoms, which can make diagnosis difficult. In addition, many diseases require complex treatment, which requires the doctor to have knowledge and skills in various fields of medicine [4-6].

In addition, the requirements for the quality of medical care remain high. Patients have the right to receive high-quality medical care. Doctors should be able to provide such assistance using modern methods of diagnosis and treatment.

The course "Modern treatment algorithms in internal medicine" allows students to gain knowledge about the most effective and safe methods of treatment of internal diseases. This allows students to be more efficient in their work and provide patients with high-quality medical care.

Here are some specific examples of the relevance of studying the course "Modern treatment algorithms in internal medicine":

Implementation of new diagnostic methods. After all, new diagnostic methods are being introduced, such as computer tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, and positron emission tomography. These methods allow doctors to more accurately diagnose internal diseases.

Development of new methods of treatment. In recent years, new methods of treatment have been developed, such as targeted therapy, immunotherapy, and biological therapy is used to treat various diseases. These methods allow more effective treatment of severe pathologies.

Changes in treatment recommendations. Recommendations for the treatment of internal diseases are constantly changing based on new research. The course "Modern algorithms of treatment in internal medicine" allows students to be aware of the latest recommendations.

Features of the course:

- **Emphasis on evidence-based medicine.** The course is based on the principles of evidence-based medicine, which means that the treatment is based on scientific research data. This allows students to gain knowledge about the most effective and safe methods of treatment.

- **Interactive learning methods.** When studying the course, interactive teaching methods are used, which allow students to actively participate in the educational process. This contributes to better assimilation of knowledge and development of practical skills.

- **Practical classes.** The course involves conducting practical classes in which students practice practical skills related to the diagnosis and treatment of diseases.

The main goals of the course:

1. Formation of students' theoretical knowledge about modern algorithms for the treatment of internal diseases.

2. Development of students' practical skills related to the diagnosis and treatment of diseases.

3. Formation of students' critical thinking skills and informed decision-making in the context of evidence-based medicine.

Expected learning outcomes. After completing the course, students will be able to:

Describe the basic principles of evidence-based medicine.

To determine the most effective and safe methods of treatment of internal diseases.

Conduct diagnosis and treatment of diseases according to modern algorithms.

Make informed decisions in the context of evidence-based medicine.

The methodology of conducting the course "Modern algorithms for diagnosis and treatment of diseases of internal organs" should ensure the achievement of the following goals: students' assimilation of theoretical knowledge about diseases of internal organs; development of practical skills in diagnosis and treatment of diseases of internal organs; formation of students' critical thinking skills and application of modern diagnostic and treatment algorithms for diseases of internal organs.

When conducting this course, in order to improve the assimilation of the material and increase the motivation for learning, the teachers use various interactive teaching methods. Interactive learning methods are methods that allow students to actively participate in the learning process. They can be used to study any subject, but are particularly effective for studying courses that require the application of practical knowledge and skills [7]. When studying the course "Modern algorithms for managing patients in the clinic of internal medicine", interactive learning methods are used for:

Acquisition of theoretical knowledge. Students can participate in virtual simulations that allow them to practice practical skills related to the diagnosis and treatment of diseases.

Development of practical skills. Participate in the work of a clinical case, in the framework of which they will diagnose and treat a patient under the guidance of a teacher.

Assessments of knowledge and skills. For example, participation in interactive tests and exercises that allow you to test their understanding of the material.

The use of interactive teaching methods when studying the course "Modern algorithms for managing patients in the clinic of internal medicine" can help students better acquire theoretical knowledge and develop practical skills. This, in turn, can lead to an increase in the quality of their training and preparation for professional activities.

Here are some advantages of using interactive learning methods:

- They improve the assimilation of knowledge. Interactive learning methods allow students to actively participate in the learning process, which contributes to better assimilation of knowledge.

- Develop practical skills. Interactive learning methods allow students to practice practical skills in a safe environment.

- Increase interest in learning. Interactive learning methods can make learning more interesting and exciting.

Of course, interactive learning methods are not a panacea. They should be used in conjunction with other learning methods, such as lectures, practical classes and independent work. The use of various teaching methods allows students to better assimilate theoretical knowledge and develop practical skills [8]. This, in turn, contributes to the improvement of the quality of their training and preparation for professional activities. Studying the course "Modern treatment algorithms in internal medicine" is an important component of training. This allows students to be more efficient in their work and provide patients with high-quality medical care. It allows students to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills for effective drug therapy of the patient.

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